

Maternal Satisfaction with Opioid-Free Versus Opioid-Based Post Caesarean Section Analgesia among Preeclamptics on Magnesium Sulphate: A Randomised Clinical Trial

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ABSTRACT

Background: While multimodal non-opioid analgesia may help reduce opioid-related side effects, opioid use can still lead to dose-dependent tolerance, dependence, and addiction in some patients, impacting maternal satisfaction. This limitation has sparked interest in opioid-free multimodal analgesia, which combines non-opioid and adjuvant analgesics on a scheduled basis, reserving opioids for rescue analgesia only. Magnesium sulfate, an adjuvant analgesic, is a suitable component of opioid-free analgesia, particularly for preeclamptic women on magnesium sulfate undergoing caesarean section, as it may contribute to improved maternal satisfaction and outcomes.

Aim: To determine and compare maternal satisfaction in opioid-free analgesia treated preeclamptic women and opioid-based analgesia treated preeclamptic women undergoing caesarean section.

Methods: Ethical approval was obtained from the research ethics committee of Federal Medical Centre, Yenagoa. The study was a superiority randomized clinical trial. One hundred preeclamptic women undergoing caesarean section who gave consent and met the eligibility criteria was enrolled into the study. Sampling method was convenience sampling. Randomization was carried out by using WINPEPI. There were two groups with 50 participants in group A (experimental arm) and 50 participants in group B (control arm). Experimental arm received postoperative intravenous paracetamol, intramuscular placebo and rectal diclofenac for 24 hours. Control arm received postoperative intramuscular pentazocine, intravenous paracetamol and rectal diclofenac for 24 hours. Rescue analgesia (intramuscular pethidine) was administered to women in this study outside the established analgesic regimen for both arms of the study if needed. A Likert scale was used to assess maternal satisfaction 24 hours post-surgery. Statistical significance was pValue <0.05.

Results: Patients in the treatment arm B reported less severe pain (0% vs. 38%), greater satisfaction with pain relief (68% vs. 28%), and a higher likelihood of recommending the treatment (68% vs. 44%). Fewer patients in the treatment arm B rated their satisfaction as poor or very poor (12% vs. 34%), and more rated it as excellent (34% vs. 0%). However, dissatisfaction with pain relief methods was prevalent in both groups (92% vs. 98%). Statistical significance was observed

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in pain experience (0% vs. 38%), satisfaction (28% vs. 68%), and perceived effectiveness (0% vs. 34%).

Conclusion: While opioid-based multimodal analgesia provided significantly better pain relief and higher maternal satisfaction, opioid-free multimodal analgesia remained a viable and acceptable alternative for postoperative pain management in preeclamptic women receiving magnesium sulphate after caesarean section.

KEYWORDS: Maternal satisfaction, Magnesium sulphate, Preeclampsia, Caesarean section, Opioid free analgesia.

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INTRODUCTION

Caesarean delivery is among the most commonly performed surgical procedures worldwide, with a steadily rising incidence, highlighting the importance of optimizing its perioperative and postoperative management.¹⁻³ Postoperative discomfort, particularly pain, is the most prevalent concern following surgery. Pain is a complex sensory and emotional experience shaped by physiological, sensory, affective, cognitive, sociocultural, and behavioral factors.^{2, 4} Although pain is an expected component of the postoperative healing process, inadequate pain control can lead to adverse outcomes. Poorly managed postoperative pain may provoke clinical and psychological disturbances, diminish quality of life, and increase morbidity and mortality.^{2, 4}

Post-caesarean section pain is a key determinant of maternal dissatisfaction and can hinder early recovery, mother–infant bonding, and overall childbirth experience.⁵⁻⁶ Inadequate pain control is associated with prolonged hospitalization, increased costs, and a higher risk of chronic pain, underscoring the importance of effective postoperative analgesia as a marker of quality care.⁵ However, pain perception and maternal satisfaction are influenced by multiple clinical and individual factors, and no single gold-standard approach to post-caesarean pain management exists.⁵⁻⁶ Pain was considered a fifth vital sign⁷ and access to pain relief is considered a human right.⁸

Patients' satisfaction with post-operative pain management is a measure of the quality of surgical care.⁷ When uncontrolled pain is experienced, it has profound negative effect on the sufferer.^{7,9} Examples of such effect in post-caesarean section patients include impairment of mother and child bonding, delayed initiation of breastfeeding, delayed ambulation and increased risk of venous thromboembolism.⁹

Although opioids have traditionally been central to postoperative analgesia^{7,8}, their use is frequently limited by adverse effects that can negatively affect maternal comfort, recovery, and overall satisfaction following caesarean delivery.⁹⁻¹² These concerns, together with the public health implications of opioid misuse, have driven a shift toward multimodal,

opioid-sparing analgesic strategies aimed at optimizing pain control while enhancing maternal satisfaction and the postoperative childbirth experience. The aim of this study is to determine and compare patient satisfaction in opioid-free analgesia treated preeclamptic women and opioid-based analgesia treated preeclamptic women undergoing caesarean section.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A single-center, superiority, randomized controlled trial (RCT). Randomization was into two equal arms. Participants were preeclamptic women undergoing Caesarean section at the Federal Medical Center Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. All procedures followed the 2013 Helsinki Declaration. The research ethics committee, Federal Medical Center Yenagoa approved the trial protocol. Each participant gave written informed consent to participate. Exclusion criteria included preeclamptic women with active peptic ulcer disease, active liver disease, hepatic failure, renal failure, previous history of ischemic heart disease/myocardial infarction, heart failure, venous thrombosis, stroke, hypersensitivity to pentazocine, paracetamol, diclofenac or magnesium sulphate, history of non-medical use (abuse) of opioids and can neither communicate in English nor Pidgin English.

INTERVENTION

After preloading, all the women received spinal anaesthesia with 2 ml [10 mg] of hyperbaric 0.5% bupivacaine into the subarachnoid space, and patients laid supine immediately. This fixed dose of bupivacaine was used instead of height and weight-adjusted dose to make the protocol easy to follow for the anaesthetist. It is backed by evidence from a randomized controlled trial showing that a fixed dose of 10 mg of hyperbaric 0.5% bupivacaine had similar results to height and weight-adjusted dose in spinal anaesthesia for caesarean section.¹³

Experimental group received a combination of parenteral magnesium sulphate (ANCALIMA®- LIFESCIENCES LTD, India) according to Pritchard regimen as follows: 4g of a 20%

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solution of magnesium sulphate as an intravenous bolus slowly over 10 minutes and 10g of 50% solution intramuscularly (5g into each buttock) as loading dose preoperatively. Thereafter, 5g of 50% solution of magnesium sulphate into alternate buttocks every 4 hours was given for 24 hours. Post-operatively; immediately after wound dressing and patient cleaning, 100 mg of suppository diclofenac (LOFENAC®-BLISS GVS PHARMA LTD, India) was administered and continued 12-hourly, intravenous paracetamol (Drugamol®-DRUGFIELD PHARMACEUTICALS LTD, Nigeria) 1g 6-hourly and intramuscular placebo 30 mg (45 mg if patient is > 70 kg) was administered 6-hourly over 24 hours post-operatively.

Control group (routine opioid-based regimen active control) received a combination of parenteral magnesium sulphate (ANCALIMA®-LIFESCIENCES LTD, India) according to Pritchard regimen, as follows: 4g of a 20% solution of magnesium sulphate as an intravenous bolus slowly over 10 minutes and 10g of 50% solution intramuscularly (5g into each buttock) as loading dose preoperatively. Thereafter, 5g of 50% solution of magnesium sulphate into alternate buttocks every 4 hours was given for 24 hours. Post-operatively; immediately after wound dressing and patient cleaning, 100 mg of suppository diclofenac (LOFENAC®-BLISS GVS PHARMA LTD, India) was administered and continued 12-hourly, intramuscular pentazocine (ZOPENT®-GREENLIFE PHARMACEUTICALS LTD, Nigeria) 30 mg (45 mg if patient is > 70 kg) was administered 6-hourly, intravenous paracetamol (Drugamol®-DRUGFIELD PHARMACEUTICALS LTD, Nigeria) 1g 6-hourly was commenced, all over 24 hours post-operatively.

Rescue analgesia was administered to women in this study outside the established analgesic regimen for both arms of the study if needed. It was administered only on patients' expression of moderate to severe pain or following an assessment of moderate to severe pain by ward nurses/research assistants, despite the planned analgesic regimen for both arms of the study. One hundred milligrams of intramuscular pethidine (MARTINDALE PHARMA, BAMPTON ROAD, HAROLD HILL, ROMFORD, RM3 8UG, UK) was used as rescue analgesia during the first 24 hours after caesarean section in both arms of the study.

PRIMARY OUTCOME MEASURE

The primary outcome measure was women that are satisfied with the analgesia

SAMPLE SIZE DETERMINATION

The calculated minimum sample size to achieve a statistical power of 80% and 5% significant level was 45. A deliberate oversampling of 10% was allowed for nonresponders/ dropouts. This gave an approximate of 50 parturient on each arm of the study.

RECRUITMENT

Patients were enrolled into the study in order of appearance, based on their eligibility and willingness to participate in the study (convenience sampling). All women being prepared for induction of labour were met by the researcher or trained assistant in the antenatal ward or labour ward. Exclusion criteria were identified through relevant information obtained from case folders and history obtained from the women. To obtain an informed consent, the researcher or a trained assistant explained the aim and processes of the study and its benefits to eligible women in simple and clear terms, and an assurance of safety was given. Participants signed the consent form for the study only after they have expressed an understanding of the study and showed willingness to participate.

RANDOMIZATION AND ALLOCATION CONCEALMENT MECHANISM

Allocation sequence generation

Using the WINPEPI software for randomization, a random and balanced allocation of numbers 1 to 100 to letters A and B was conducted. Intervention arm A was designated the experimental group and intervention arm B was designated the control group. The women were allocated to receive either a preventive opioid-free multimodal analgesia regimen in the intervention arm A (experimental) or a routine post-operative, opioid-based multimodal analgesia regimen in the intervention arm B (control).

Allocation concealment mechanism

Identical, sealed, sequentially arranged and opaque envelopes had cards inscribed with letter A or B concealed within them according to the randomly assigned letter to each number from 1 to 100. These envelopes were labelled outwardly using serial numbers from 1 to 100.

Implementation

As each eligible woman is received into the theatre for a caesarean section, a research assistant picks an envelope according to the sequence. The number inscribed on the card in the envelope was announced and shown to the researcher, anaesthetist and peri-operative nurse (A = experimental arm and B = control arm). The serial number / identification number

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on the envelope selected was attached to the case folder, operation note and other documents for the study.

Blinding

The participants, researcher, research assistants, nurses who administered the post-operative analgesics and assess the post-operative pain intensity of the women and those responsible for data entry were all blinded in this study except the pharmacist preparing the drugs. All the trial documents were concealed in an opaque envelope on the ward.

Data collection methods

Patient satisfaction was assessed using the Likert scale. Twenty-four hours post caesarean section the patients were asked to indicate the numeric value from 1 to 10 that signifies the level of her satisfaction with the analgesia graphically or verbally; where 1 and 2 means very poor satisfaction; 3 and 4 poor satisfactions; 5 and 6 good satisfactions; 7 and 8 very good satisfaction; 9 and 10 excellent satisfaction.

Data management

SPSS spreadsheet was used for data management. Data entry from paper data collection instruments into the SPSS spreadsheet was done weekly.

Data Monitoring

Full compliance with the trial monitoring mechanism of the study Centre was ensured.

DATA ANALYSIS

An intention-to-treat (ITT) analysis will be employed. Statistical analysis of the data obtained from the study was done

using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. Frequencies and percentages of categorical data was determined. Mean and standard deviation of continuous numerical data, median, mode and range of discrete numerical data was determined. Comparisons between experimental and control groups was done using Chi-square test of proportions for categorical data, Student 't' test for normally distributed continuous data. A p-value < 0.05 will be considered significant statistically.

RESULTS

Three hundred and sixty-seven women booked for caesarean section at the Obstetrics and Gynaecology department of Federal Medical Centre, Yenagoa, during the study period and one hundred and eight of them were identified as potential participants presenting with preeclampsia. However, six of these women were excluded due to at least one of the exclusion criteria and two women declined to participate in the study.

One hundred women were ultimately enrolled in the study and randomly assigned to one of two study arms in a 1:1 ratio. The two arms consisted of an experimental group (Arm A) and a control group (Arm B). In the experimental group (Arm A), 50 women were assigned to receive the intervention and were assessed for primary and secondary outcome measures. In the control group (Arm B), all 50 women assigned to the control group (Arm B) received the intended intervention and were assessed for primary and secondary outcome measures. Consequently, data from all 100 enrolled women were included in the final analysis.

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Figure 1: Study Flow Diagram

Table 1: Sociodemographic data of participants

Variable	Treatment Arm A		Treatment Arm B		Significance Test	p-value
	Freq (N=50)	%	Freq (N=50)	%		
Age (years)						
• 20-24	1	2.0	0	0.0	4.35 ^a	0.210
• 25-29	13	26.0	17	34.0		
• 30-34	23	46.0	15	30.0		
• 35-39	13	26.0	18	36.0		
Mean age ± SD	31.92 ± 3.60 yrs		30.76 ± 4.05 yrs		1.12 ^b	0.254

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Mean weight ± SD	83.84 ± 12.41 kg	78.64 ± 9.32 kg	2.82 ^b	0.063
Ethnicity				
• Igbo	22	44.0	19	38.0
• Ijaw	22	44.0	21	42.0
• Others	6	12.0	10	20.0
Parity				
• Nulliparous	7	14.0	10	20.0
• Primiparous	10	20.0	7	14.0
• Multiparous	33	66.0	33	66.0

^a Chi-square test, ^b Student's t Test, *Statistically significant

The socio-demographic data of participants revealed comparable characteristics between Treatment Arms A and B. The mean age was slightly higher in Arm A (31.92 ± 3.60 years) than in Arm B (30.76 ± 4.05 years), with no significant difference (p = 0.254). Arm A participants had a higher mean weight (83.84 ± 12.41 kg) than Arm B which is not statistically

significant (78.64 ± 9.32 kg, p = 0.063). Ethnicity and parity distributions were similar across groups, with Igbo and Ijaw being the predominant ethnicities, and most participants being multiparous. There were no significant differences in age categories, ethnicity, or parity between the groups.

Table 2: Clinical data of participants

Variable	Treatment Arm A		Treatment Arm B		X ²	p-value
	Freq (N = 50)	%	Freq (N = 50)	%		
Previous CS						
• No	26	52.0	28	56.0	0.48	0.487
• Yes	24	48.0	22	44.0		
	N = 24		N = 22			
Number of previous CS						
• 1	17	70.8	13	59.1	0.64	0.423
• 2	7	29.2	9	40.9		

The clinical data showed no significant differences between Treatment Arms A and B regarding previous cesarean sections (CS). A similar proportion of participants in Arm A (48.0%) and Arm B (44.0%) had a history of CS (p = 0.487). Among

those with a previous CS, the majority in both groups had undergone only one prior CS (70.8% in Arm A vs. 59.1% in Arm B), with no significant difference in the number of previous CS between the arms (p = 0.423).

Table 3: Patient satisfaction with analgesia regimen in the Treatment arms A and B

		Treatment	Treatment	X ²
		Arm A	Arm B	
What type of pain did you expect in the postoperative period	None	6 (12.0)	6 (12.0)	.00
	Mild	7 (14.0)	21 (42.0)	
	Moderate	18 (36.0)	23 (46.0)	
	Severe	19 (38.0)	0 (0.0)	
What type of pain did you experience in the postoperative period	None	4 (8.0)	16 (32.0)	.02
	Mild	13 (26.0)	10 (20.0)	
	Moderate	22 (44.0)	19 (38.0)	

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	Severe	11 (22.0)	5 (10.0)	
When you were in pain, nurses and doctors responded	No	4 (8.0)	1 (2.0)	.17
	Yes	46 (92.0)	49 (98.0)	
Would you recommend the pain relief administered to you	No	13 (26.0)	7 (14.0)	.05
	Yes	22 (44.0)	34 (68.0)	
	Not sure	15 (30.0)	9 (18.0)	
Did the pain relief received meet your expectation for pain relief	No	21 (42.0)	7 (14.0)	.00
	Yes	14 (28.0)	34 (68.0)	
	Not sure	15 (30.0)	9 (18.0)	
Is there something you don't like about the pain relief	Yes	46 (92.0)	49 (98.0)	.17
	No	4 (8.0)	1 (2.0)	
How would you rate the satisfaction from the pain relief administered	Very poor	2 (4.0)	0 (0.0)	.00
	Poor	15 (30.0)	6 (12.0)	
	Good	21 (42.0)	13 (26.0)	
	Very good	12 (24.0)	14 (28.0)	
	Excellent	0 (0.0)	17 (34.0)	

Patients in the treatment arm B reported less severe pain (0% vs. 38%), greater satisfaction with pain relief (68% vs. 28%), and a higher likelihood of recommending the treatment (68% vs. 44%). Fewer patients in the treatment arm B rated their satisfaction as poor or very poor (12% vs. 34%), and more rated it as excellent (34% vs. 0%). However, dissatisfaction with pain relief methods was prevalent in both groups (92% vs. 98%). Statistical significance was observed in pain experience (0% vs. 38%), satisfaction (28% vs. 68%), and perceived effectiveness (0% vs. 34%).

DISCUSSION

This study revealed a significant difference in patients' satisfaction with analgesia between women receiving preventive, opioid-free, multimodal analgesia and the opioid-based, multimodal analgesia group, with the opioid-based multimodal analgesia group reporting higher satisfaction levels. This finding aligns with the results of a study conducted by Jun et al¹⁴, which demonstrated a positive correlation between patients' satisfaction with increased opioid analgesia. This may be due to reduce discomfort, anxiety, and stress related to pain produced by opioids resulting in higher patient satisfaction. Opioids can have anxiolytic effects and improve sleep quality, which is essential for recovery and overall satisfaction. Opioid analgesia may also increase feelings of relaxation and well-

being, leading to higher patient satisfaction. The finding however differs from a study by Adebisi et al¹⁵ where the overall satisfaction of the participants with postoperative pain management was similar in both groups and was attributed to the effective multimodal analgesic regimen of diclofenac, acetaminophen and rescue pentazocine used in the study. Adamou et al¹⁶ in a randomized controlled trial of opioid only versus combined opioid and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory analgesics for pain relief in the first 48 hours after Caesarean section reported that the use of combined analgesia compared to single-agent analgesia is safe, significantly reduced pain and improved patient satisfaction during post-operative period following Caesarean section.

Patients' satisfaction with analgesia is a multifaceted concept influenced by various factors beyond pain management alone. These factors include patient expectations, level of information provided, baseline physical and psychological status, and the quality of communication and interaction with healthcare providers. A study by Mubita et al¹⁷ highlights the significance of effective pain management in enhancing patient satisfaction which is influenced by good communication and information transfer, appropriate pain management and an empathic presence throughout. The study found that patients who received adequate pain control were more likely to be satisfied with their care. Furthermore, when patients perceived

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healthcare staff as making sufficient efforts to relieve pain, their satisfaction levels increase. These findings underscore the importance of effective pain management and patient-centered care in enhancing patient satisfaction and overall healthcare experience.

STRENGTHS AND LIMITATIONS

The study used primary data, which gave precise information. The randomized clinical trial design of this study gives a high level of evidence and also reduces bias. Bias was reduced by randomization, blinding, use of standardized methods for data collection and analysis, as well as data quality control.

The limitation is findings may not be generalizable to other populations, as it was conducted exclusively among preeclamptic women undergoing caesarean sections at a single hospital, the Federal Medical Centre Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

CONCLUSION

While opioid-based multimodal analgesia provided significantly better pain relief and higher maternal satisfaction, opioid-free multimodal analgesia remained a viable and acceptable alternative for postoperative pain management in preeclamptic women receiving magnesium sulphate after caesarean section.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Opioid-based multimodal analgesia should remain the preferred option for post-caesarean pain control in preeclamptic women when not contraindicated, due to higher maternal satisfaction and better pain relief. However, opioid-free multimodal analgesia may serve as a suitable alternative or adjunct in selected patients, particularly those at risk of opioid-related adverse effects or where opioids are limited. Postoperative analgesia should be individualized, supported by adequate preoperative counseling to improve satisfaction. Further multicenter studies are recommended to guide evidence-based policies on opioid-sparing analgesia in obstetric care.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Idea/Concept: Atemie Gordon, Warisuo S. Ariwelo, Ozori E. Stanley; Design: Atemie Gordon, Warisuo S. Ariwelo, Ozori E. Stanley, Akanatei I Daniel; Control/Supervision: Atemie Gordon, Porbeni-Fumudoh B. Offiong, Amadi-Oyioma M Chigesilem; Data Collection and/or Processing: Atemie Gordon, Porbeni-Fumudoh B. Offiong, Amadi-Oyioma M Chigesilem, Feghabo J Ebiegberi; Analysis and/or Interpretation: Atemie Gordon, Feghabo J Ebiegberi, Sintei

Erigheyefa; Literature Review: Atemie Gordon, Amadi-Oyioma M Chigesilem, Feghabo J Ebiegberi, Sintei Erigheyefa; Writing the Article: Atemie Gordon; Critical Review: Atemie Gordon, Warisuo S. Ariwelo, Ozori E. Stanley, Akanatei I Daniel, Porbeni-Fumudoh B. Offiong, Amadi-Oyioma M Chigesilem, Feghabo J Ebiegberi, Sintei Erigheyefa

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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ETHICAL APPROVAL

Ethical approval was obtained from the ethical committee of the Federal Medical Centre, Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

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